

Supplementary Fig. S9 The segregation of the monosomic chromosome 5B in DH_{1:2} progeny of StanleyLandmarkDH01038-0. The DH_{0:1} plant StanleyLandmarkDH01038-0 derived from selfing of primary DH line was selfed to produce six DH_{1:2} progenies. The segregation was identified as monosomic (DH01038-0-5 and DH01038-0-6) and disomic (DH01038-0-1, DH01038-0-2, DH01038-0-3, and DH01038-0-4) by digital karyotyping. Each panel shows the genomic position of a given chromosome in 1Mb bins on the physical map of the CDC Landmark reference genome in the x-axis with points showing the normalized number of reads mapping to the respective bin. The vertical axis shows both normalized read count (left) and chromosome dosage (right). The parental allele for individual SNP variants is shown on top for CDC Landmark (red) and CDC Stanley (blue) alleles. Centromere positions are showing as black triangle.